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Support of the Veterinary Services of Poland to investigate potential risk factors for African Swine Fever (ASF) incursion in commercial pig herds

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Abstract

The aim of the project was to investigate potential risk factors for African Swine Fever (ASFV) incursion in commercial pig herds in Poland. In total, 19 case farms and 36 control farms have been tested in the years 2022-2023. Sampling resulted in collection of 5358 insects (4745 *Culicoides* ssp. and 613 *Stomoxys* ssp.) that were subsequently divided into 551 pools of *Culicoides* ssp. and 163 pools of *Stomoxys* ssp. All samples were analysed for the presence of ASFV genetic material and β -actin by real-time PCR. Samples positive for ASFV genome were subjected to virus isolation on porcine primary pulmonary alveolar macrophages. The presence of ASFV DNA was detected in one sample of *Stomoxys* ssp. pool from the control farm in Wrocławski region (PL518) in 2022 and in two samples of *Stomoxys* ssp. pools from two different outbreak farms in Bialski region (PL811) in 2023. These samples were subjected to further virus isolation and the results were negative. In 2023 the presence of ASFV DNA was also detected in three samples of *Culicoides* ssp. pools from three different region – Elbląski (PL621), Bialski (PL811) and Puławski (PL815) but their too high Ct values excluded them from virus isolation. Also, β -actin, a genetic marker for pig DNA, was identified in 14.72% of *Stomoxys* ssp. samples and in 17.24% of *Culicoides* ssp. samples. These results may suggest low risk of ASFV introduction by the analysed species of insects. Most probably, *Stomoxys* spp. and *Culicoides* spp. may only serve as mechanical vectors of ASF. Further studies are recommended to investigate the role of other vectors/fomites in ASF epidemiology.

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Keywords: African swine fever, pigs, vectors, stable flies, biting midges, incursion, outbreak

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Summary

The aim of the project was to investigate potential risk factors for African Swine Fever (ASFV) incursion in commercial pig herds in Poland. In total, 19 case farms and 36 control farms have been tested in the years 2022-2023. Each sampling was carried out with the completion of a detailed questionnaire containing questions about the conditions on the farm and its surrounding. Sampling resulted in collection of 5358 insects (4 745 *Culicoides* ssp. and 613 *Stomoxys* ssp.) that were subsequently divided into 551 pools of *Culicoides* ssp. and 163 pools of *Stomoxys* ssp. All samples were analysed for the presence of ASFV genetic material and β -actin by real-time PCR. ASFV-positive samples were subjected to virus isolation on porcine primary pulmonary alveolar macrophages.

The presence of ASFV DNA was detected in one sample of *Stomoxys* ssp. pool from the control farm in Wrocławski region (PL518) in 2022 and in two samples of *Stomoxys* ssp. pools from two different outbreak farms in Bialski region (PL811) in 2023. These samples were subjected to further virus isolation and the results were negative.

The presence of ASFV DNA was also detected in three samples of *Culicoides* ssp. pools from three different region – Elbląski (PL621), Bialski (PL811) and Puławski (PL815). These samples reached Ct values >37 which was too high to attempt virus isolation.

β -actin was identified in 14.72% of *Stomoxys* ssp. samples and in 17.24% of *Culicoides* ssp. samples, demonstrating the presence of pig DNA.

These data suggest low risk of ASFV introduction by the analysed species of insects. Most probably, *Stomoxys* ssp. and *Culicoides* ssp. may only serve as mechanical vectors of ASF.

Further studies are recommended to investigate the role of other vectors/fomites in ASF pathogenesis.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background and terms of reference as provided by the requestor

This contract/grant was awarded by EFSA to: National Veterinary Research Institute

Contractor/Beneficiary: National Veterinary Research Institute

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2 Data and methodologies

2.1 Data

The objectives of this project were as follows:

1. to investigate the potential risk for ASF incursion in domestic pig herds of different herd types and/or size;
2. to investigate the possible involvement of vectors in the transmission of African swine fever.

The number of ASF outbreaks in pigs in Poland in the consecutive years was as follows: 124 (in 2021), 14 (in 2022) and 30 (in 2023). However, due to the prolonged process of acquiring suitable personnel within the resources of the Veterinary Inspection, the sampling started in 2022 and was performed until the end of 2023.

During 2021-2022 only commercial pig farms of 30 or more pigs were included in the study, however, due to very few ASF outbreaks in eligible commercial farms, in 2023 farms with 10 and more pigs bred for commercial purposes were also included. This was done to increase study power as the number of ASF outbreaks has been considerably lower than estimated. For each outbreak farm, two matched control farms were randomly selected, matched by herd size (i.e. 10-29; 30-199; 200-1000; >1000). If a control farm was not available in the same county it was selected from a neighbouring county.

More specifically, in 2022, the number of 14 ASF outbreaks occurred in the domestic pig population in Poland. Only 8 outbreaks met the conditions necessary to be included in the project. In 2023, 30 outbreaks were confirmed, of which 11 were included. Finally, between 2022 and 2023, the total number of 19 ASF outbreaks in domestic pigs were included in the analyses. For all those case farms, controls have been designated.

In 2022 sampling was conducted in 8 outbreaks and 16 control farms. Vector samples were obtained from 8 ASF outbreaks and 16 control farms. All farms were located in 3 voivodeships – Wielkopolskie, Warmińsko-Mazurskie and Dolnośląskie and 8 counties by NUTS 3 code –

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Pilski (PL411), Koniński (PL414), Kaliski (PL416), Leszczyński (PL417), Poznański (PL418), Legnicko-Głogowski (PL516), Elbląski (PL621) and Wrocławski (PL518). The collected vectors were grouped into 166 biting midges (*Culicoides* ssp.) pools and 64 stable flies (*Stomoxys* ssp.) pools.

In 2023 sampling was conducted in 11 outbreaks and 20 control farms. Vector samples were obtained from 10 ASF outbreaks and 20 control farms. On one outbreak farm sampling was unsuccessful due to independent, adverse conditions for vector sampling. All farms were located in 3 voivodeships – Wielkopolskie, Warmińsko-Mazurskie and Lubelskie and 7 counties by NUTS 3 code – Kaliski (PL416), Leszczyński (PL417), Elbląski (PL621), Ełcki (PL623), Bialski (PL811), Lubelski (PL814) and Puławski (PL815). The collected vectors were grouped into 385 *Culicoides* ssp. pools and 99 *Stomoxys* ssp. pools.

In total, 4745 insects grouped into 551 pools of *Culicoides* ssp. and 613 insects grouped into 163 pools of *Stomoxys* ssp. were analyzed in 2022-2023 (Table 1).

Table 1: Number of individual vector pools collected in 2022-2023 in particular NUTS 3 regions

NUTS 3 code	2022 ^(a)		2023 ^(b)	
	<i>Stomoxys</i> ssp.	<i>Culicoides</i> ssp.	<i>Stomoxys</i> ssp.	<i>Culicoides</i> ssp.
PL411	1	20	-	-
PL414	8	15	-	-
PL416	21	27	14	19
PL417	9	55	8	38
PL418	0	1	-	-
PL516	5	4	-	-
PL518	10	18	-	-
PL621	10	26	3	49
PL623	-	-	0	1
PL811	-	-	20	148
PL814	-	-	45	77
PL815	-	-	9	53
TOTAL	64	166	99	385

- not applicable

(a): Number of insect pools collected in 2022

(b): Number of insect pools collected in 2023

2.2 Methodologies

Sampling was carried out by the trained employees of the Veterinary Inspection. As soon as confirmations of African Swine Fever (ASF) were obtained, the appropriate personnel from the Veterinary Inspection was dispatched to the farm to collect samples and gather data for the survey.

For each outbreak farm, 2 matched control farms were randomly found, matching in size and location. If possible, they were selected from the same affected county, eventually from the neighbouring county.

After each confirmation of ASF, in the affected farm questionnaires were carried out without delay, not later than 48 hours. In the 2 matching control farms questionnaires were performed within 1 week after confirmation of the case farm.

Samples and questionnaires from case and control farms has been sent to the National Veterinary Research Institute (NVRI) in Pulawy.

The questionnaires and data of sampled farms were subsequently uploaded into the database.

The initial identification and segregation of vectors were performed by the qualified staff of the BSL-2 laboratory of the Department of Virology (National Veterinary Research Institute in Pulawy, NVRI, Poland). Subsequently, the laboratory analyses, including samples preparation, DNA extractions, molecular testing and virus isolations, were carried out by qualified personnel of the BLS-3 laboratory located at the National Reference Laboratory for ASF (NRL), in Department of Swine Diseases (NVRI in Pulawy, Poland).

2.2.1 Collection of vectors

A set of traps and accessories necessary for catching vectors have been placed in strategic Veterinary Inspectorates. Following the confirmation of the outbreak in the commercial pig farm by NRL, the Veterinary Inspection staff responsible for sampling in the given area was informed. The trapping procedure was conducted in the ASF outbreak farm as well as in two control farms randomly selected by EFSA, matching in herd size and county. Traps in the outbreak farms were placed before slaughter of the pigs and disinfection of units. If this was not possible, traps were set during slaughter and disinfection, or up to 36 hours after the slaughter of the last animal. Traps in the connected control farms were placed within a week after the outbreak confirmation.

Two traps (inside and outside the building) for *Culicoides* ssp. were set in the evening and removed the next morning. The commercial traps were equipped with a UV light source and a container with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS). Traps were switched on 1h before sunset and switched off 1h after sunrise. The UV traps were installed at a standardized height: the UV tube was placed at a height of 1.5 to 2 meters from the ground.

Four fly papers (two inside and two outside the building) for *Stomoxys* ssp. were set in 4 different locations in the morning and removed the same day in the evening. In each location traps were placed at a distance of minimum 15 meters from each other, in an area of heavy

fly activity, in direct sunlight to maximize traps visibility to stable flies. The traps were placed outside, near the animals, at maximum 15 m, at a 1.6 m height.

In total, six containers of *Culicoides* spp. and 12 flypapers of *Stomoxys* spp. were obtained from sampling in one outbreak and two control farms. The collected samples were sent to NVRI in Pulawy for testing.

2.2.2 Vectors identification

Flies and biting midges were sorted out from other insects and used for morphological identification. An Olympus SZX16 binocular stereoscopic microscope was used to identify biting midges, and a magnifying loupe was used to identify flies. Identification was based on general appearance, such as size, shape, color, character of the antennae, legs, wings, and bristles. Arthropods were identified by general appearance as belonging to a particular order or family group, but further identification often required examination of individual parts of the specimens. The insect order, family and specific species were identified.

Stable flies (*Stomoxys calcitrans*)

Adult individuals of the species *Stomoxys calcitrans* are gray in color and 4–7 mm in size. Typical for these insects is having four black stripes on the thorax and black checkered abdomen. The most characteristic feature of *Stomoxys calcitrans* is the sword-like proboscis protruding from under the head (Zumpt 1973; Foil and Hogsette 1994) which is used to pierce the skin and imbibe blood.

Biting midges (*Culicoides* spp.)

Identification of biting midges included many morphological characteristics, metric traits, non-metric traits and the pigmentation pattern of the wings (Mathieu et al. 2012).

2.2.3 Samples preparation and DNA extraction

During vector identification all vectors we grouped in pools. Each pool referred to insects belonging to the same species, collected on the same site and at the same sampling event. All pools contained 1-4 *Stomoxys* spp. and 1-20 *Culicoides* spp. Before pooling of stable flies, each individual insect was cut into two longitudinal halves, so two identical aliquats were resulted from each group, which were then homogenized. Pools of biting midges were divided in half after homogenization. Homogenization was performed using TissueLyser II (QIAGEN, Hilden, Germany) with PBS to obtain a 10% homogenate. The DNA manual extraction was made with using the QIAamp DNA Mini Kit (QIAGEN, Hilden, Germany), according to the instruction for use the kit. Obtained homogenate was stored at <-70°C, while the DNA that was not immediately used for further analyses was kept at -20°C.

2.2.4 ASFV DNA detection

The real-time PCR test for detection the genetic material of ASF virus was performed using the Virotype ASFV PCR Kit (96) (Indical, Leipzig, Germany), according to the manufacturer's instruction. The kit allows for the identification the ASFV DNA and β -actin (host control –

swine DNA) coding sequence in the same reaction (duplex system). The amplification process was conducted in three different types of thermocyclers: Applied Biosystems 7500 (Applied Biosystems, Waltham, MA, USA), QuantStudio™5 (ThermoFisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) and Rotor-Gene Q (QIAGEN, Hilden, Germany). Samples with a fluorescent signal in the FAM channel were considered as positive. Depending on the threshold cycle value (Ct), some of the positive samples were included in subsequent tests.

2.2.5 Virus isolation

Three samples of *Stomoxys* spp. pools with the lowest Ct values were selected for virus isolation: one originated from a control farm in Wrocławski region (collected in 2022), which was the only one to show fluorescence in the FAM channel and two other samples were collected in two different outbreak farms in Bialski region, in 2023. Also, a total of ten positive *Culicoides* spp. samples collected in 2022-2023 and provided by the University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine of Cluj-Napoca (Romania) were included in the study.

Each sample was filtered by 0.45 µl filter (Sartorius, Goettingen, Germany). For the virus isolation porcine primary pulmonary alveolar macrophages (PPAM) were used. PPAMs were cultured in RPMI (Gibco, Waltham, USA), with 10% of fetal bovine serum (Gibco, Waltham, USA), 1% of Antibiotic-Antimycotic solution (Sigma Aldrich, St. Louis, USA). Cells were placed into 24-well plates and infected by the tested samples in 3 replicates. Plates were incubated at 37°C in 5% CO₂. The virus isolation results were monitored at 0-, 4- and 7-days post inoculation (dpi) with using a real-time PCR test.

3 Assessment/Results

Overall, in the years 2022-2023, 55 Polish pig commercial farms from 12 NUTS3 have been analysed. The detailed location is presented below (Figure 1). Total number of analysed pig farms including NUTS 3 code and county name is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Localization of the analysed Polish pig farms in 2022 (red) and 2023 (yellow).

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Count of farm ID by NUTS3 code and county name

Figure 2: Total number of the analysed pig farms including NUTS 3 codes and county names

In total, 19 case farms and 36 control farms have been tested. The distribution of the analysed pig farms divided into case and control farms is presented in figure 3.

Figure 3: Localization and number of pig farms that were surveyed, including the division into case (blue dots) and control (yellow dots) farms.

The farms tested in 2022 were mainly located in the eastern part of Poland, while in 2023 the majority of farms from the western part of the country were analysed and few from the north of Poland (Figure 1).

In total, 5358 insects were collected and examined, including 4 745 *Culicoides* ssp. and 613 *Stomoxys* ssp., 551 pools of *Culicoides* ssp. and 163 pools of *Stomoxys* ssp. were obtained. All samples were analysed for the presence of ASFV genetic material.

In 2022, the presence of ASFV DNA was detected in one sample of *Stomoxys* ssp. pool (*Stomoxys* 23208/1). The pool contained 4 insects from control farm in Wrocławski region (PL518). The obtained result of 37.75 Ct was considered as weak positive and output sample of homogenate was subjected to further virus isolation. In the same study, nine positive *Culicoides* ssp. samples from Romania (University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine of Cluj-Napoca, Romania) were also included. The real-time PCR results obtained at

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0, 4 and 7 dpi ruled out virus replication (Table 2). Isolation of active virus on the PPAMs was unsuccessful.

In 2023, the presence of ASFV genetic material was detected in two samples of *Stomoxys* spp. pools (*Stomoxys* 26720(13); *Stomoxys* 26721(12)) and three samples of *Culicoides* spp. pools. Both *Stomoxys* spp. pools contained 2 insects and came from two different outbreak farms in Bialski region (PL811). Both samples with 32.05 Ct (*Stomoxys* 26720(13)) and 34.21 Ct (*Stomoxys* 26721(12)) were qualified for virus isolation. In the same study, one positive *Culicoides* spp. sample from Romania was also included. The remaining three *Culicoides* spp. samples with a Ct value >37 were not selected for further testing due to too high Ct value (Gallardo et al. 2015). As previously, the real-time PCR results obtained at 0, 4 and 7 dpi ruled out virus replication (Table 2). *Stomoxys* 26720(12) sample with a value of 36.69 Ct at 7 dpi was subjected to further analysis, which did not confirm the presence of active ASF virus.

β -actin was identified in 14.72% of *Stomoxys* spp. samples and in 17.24% of *Culicoides* spp. samples.

Table 2: Results of virus isolation at 0, 4 and 7 dpi performed with Polish and Romanian samples from 2022 and 2023.

Sample name	Threshold cycle value (Ct) ^(a)		
	0 dpi	4 dpi	7 dpi
<i>Stomoxys</i> 23208/1 (Poland, 2022)	NoCt	NoCt	NoCt
<i>Ro-URZ-IL C. punctatus</i> 4-10 (Romania, 2022)	NoCt	NoCt	NoCt
<i>Ro-URZ-IL C. newsteadi</i> 4-17 (Romania, 2022)	NoCt	NoCt	NoCt
<i>Ro-CON-OT C. punctatus</i> 5-20 (Romania, 2022)	NoCt	NoCt	NoCt
<i>Ro-URZ-IL C. punctatus</i> 4-3 (Romania, 2022)	35.49	NoCt	NoCt
<i>Ro-URZ-IL C. newsteadi</i> 4-11 (Romania, 2022)	34.54	NoCt	NoCt
<i>Ro-CON-OT C. punctatus</i> 5-25 (Romania, 2022)	35.18	NoCt	NoCt
<i>Ro-CON-OT C. punctatus</i> 5-24 (Romania, 2022)	38.05	NoCt	NoCt
<i>Ro-CON-OT C. punctatus</i> 5-26 (Romania, 2022)	36.51	NoCt	NoCt
<i>Ro-CON-OT C. punctatus</i> 5-28 (Romania, 2022)	NoCt	NoCt	NoCt
<i>Stomoxys</i> 26720(13) (Poland, 2023)	33.57	36.1	NoCt
<i>Stomoxys</i> 26721(12) (Poland, 2023)	NoCt	NoCt	36.69
<i>Ro-RII4 Culicoides</i> (Romania, 2023)	NoCt	NoCt	NoCt

(a): Mean Ct value obtained in 3 replicates

4 Conclusion

This study enabled to sample commercial pigs farms in Poland that experienced ASF outbreaks as well as control farms and to analyse insects: *Stomoxys* spp. and *Culicoides* spp. from these farms as possible vectors of the disease.

Only in few cases ASFV genetic material was confirmed in insects, but virus replication failed in all of them. These data indicate low risk of ASFV introduction by the analysed species of insects. Most probably, *Stomoxys* spp. and *Culicoides* spp. may only serve as mechanical vectors of ASF.

5 Recommendations

Further studies are recommended to investigate the role of other vectors/fomites in ASF pathogenesis.

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Glossary [and/or] Abbreviations

ASF	African swine fever
BSL-2	Biosafety level 2
BSL-3	Biosafety level 3
CT	Cycle threshold
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
DPI	Day post inoculation
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
MA	Massachusetts
NVRI	National Veterinary Research Institute
NRL	National Reference Laboratory
NUTS	Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics
PBS	Phosphate-buffered saline
PCR	Polymerase chain reaction
PL	Poland
PPAM	Primary pulmonary alveolar macrophages
RPMI	Roswell Park Memorial Institute medium
SP.	Species
SPP.	Species (plural)
USA	United States of America
UV	Ultraviolet

Annex A – Questionnaire on ASF in domestic pig farms in Romania/Lithuania/Poland

Questionnaire on ASF in domestic pig farms in Romania/Lithuania/Poland

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

OBJECTIVES

The purpose of this survey is to collect epidemiological data as well as any available information on the development of ASF in Romania/Poland/Lithuania to:

- Perform an analysis of the temporal and spatial patterns of ASF in domestic pigs, and
- Analyse the risk factors involved in the occurrence of ASF virus in **commercial pig farms**

INSTRUCTIONS

Please, carefully read the instructions before completing the questionnaire.

- A commercial pig farm is a holding where pigs are bred for commercial purposes. For this study, **only commercial pig farms of 30 or more pigs will be included.**
- Case (outbreak) farms will be farms where ASF has been confirmed.
- A list of 10 randomly selected control farms from the same county as case farm will be provided, matching on size (e.g. 30-200; 201-1000; >1000) each case farm. If a holding is selected as control holding, but preventive culling has been applied, or the control holding is suspected or has become (in the meanwhile) positive, please go to the next control holding on the list provided.
- High Risk Period (HRP) is defined as the length of time between possible introduction date and detection of the disease, during which no control measures have yet been implemented and disease continues to spread. To harmonize answers, we have arbitrarily defined a time lapse of 6 weeks.
- Note that you will be asked to provide the GPS location of the holding. Please, be equipped with a device that can retrieve this information (e.g. smartphone), or, if not possible to use a device, complete this information before the visit.

FIRST PART: TO BE FILLED IN BEFORE THE VISIT of the HOLDING by the **team member** appointed to perform the survey

* 1. Please, select your country:

- Lithuania
- Poland
- Romania

* 2. Full name of team member appointed to carry out the questionnaire:

* 3. Email address:

Information about the holding

* 4. Holding ID:

* 5. Disease status of pig herd

- Outbreak
- Control

* 6. If outbreak holding, kindly provide the date of ASF confirmation:

* 7. If control holding, kindly provide:

a. the case farm holding ID to which this control farm was associated

b. the date of the outbreak

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* 8. Poland county (NUTS3) code:

SECOND PART: to be filled in DURING the visit

11. GPS coordinates (WGS84 coordinate system):

Example: Barcelona (Spain) has coordinates 41.403380 latitude, 2.174030 longitude

* Latitude

* Longitude

* 12. Date of the visit

Holding animals' information

* 13. Kindly provide the total number of pigs in the holding (all animals including sucklers):

* 14. Please, specify the number of each kind of pigs in the holding:

Small sucklers in farrowing boxes/pens (please provide an estimate if the exact number is not known):

* Weaned piglets (7-30 kg = piglets before they go to fattening)

* Breeding sows:

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* Breeding boars:

* Fattening male pigs:

* Fattening female pigs:

* Fattening pigs (when sex is unknown):

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* 15. Where are the pigs slaughtered?

- On the holding (including own slaughterhouse)
- In a contracted slaughterhouse
- No slaughter on farm (for example if they are all sold)

* 16. Does the farm owner have other pig farms?

- Yes
- No

* If yes, which is their holding ID?

--

* 17. Are there other animal species bred/kept IN the pig holding?

More than one answer is possible

- Bovine
- Ovine
- Caprine
- Poultry
- Horses
- Pets (dogs, cats)
- Rabbits
- Other
- No other species

* If other, please, specify which and the number of each species:

--

* 18. Are there other animal species bred/kept OUTSIDE the pig holding?

More than one answer is possible

- Bovine
- Ovine

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- Caprine
- Poultry
- Horses
- Pets (dogs, cats)
- Rabbits
- Other
- No other species

Wild boar information

* 19. Have you, or somebody else, ever seen a wild boar or other pigs roaming near (i.e. within 100 m) your farm?

- Yes
- No

* 20. Did you ever notice crossbred pigs born in your holding?

- Yes
- No

* 21. Have you, or somebody else, ever seen a wild boar body / body remains in the vicinity of your farm?

- Yes
- No

* If yes, at what distance?

[please provide an estimate if you don't know the exact distance]

m

* 22. Could a wild boar access the feed storage?

- Yes
- No

* 23. Could a wild boar access the bedding storage?

- Yes
- No

* 24. Are there any attractive feed sources for wild boar (e.g. crops or trees) around/near (i.e. within 100 m) the holding?

- Yes
- No

* If yes, please specify which type of feed source:

- Maize
- Fruit trees
- Oak trees
- Other

* 25. Is there any wild boar baiting or feeding site in the surroundings (i.e. within 100 m) of the farm

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(even if forbidden)?

- Yes
- No

Feed and drinking water

* 26. What type of feed is given on your holding?

More than one answer is possible

- Industrial compound feed: mesh
- Hay
- Industrial compound feed: pellets
- Fresh grass
- Wet feed (for example buttermilk, whey)
- On-farm milling and mixture
- Cereals (including cereals used in your own on-farm milling and mixtures)

* Please specify the municipality/ies where cereals have been grown. If not known, write "I don't know"

* Please specify the municipality/ies where hay have been grown. If not known, write "I don't know"

* Please specify the municipality/ies where grass have been grown. If not known, write "I don't know"

* 27. Are there any signs of use of kitchen waste (to be answered by official vet)?

- Yes
- No

* 28. Do you feed kitchen waste (to be answered by farmer)?

- Yes
- No

* 29. What kind of drinking water is provided to the animals?

More than one answer is possible

- Fountain water (pumped from groundwater)
- Rain water stored in holding's own reservoir (e.g. tank, container, basin...)
- River/lake water
- Tap water (drinking / cleaning / disinfected water)

* If option 2 is selected, do wild boars have access to water reservoir?

- Yes

- No

Biosecurity

* 30. Did pigs have access to any type of outdoor areas on your holding within the last 6 weeks before the confirmation of ASF on the case farm (or the corresponding case farm in case the interview is on a control farm)?

- Yes
- No

* If yes, please specify the type of outdoor farm:

- Pigs have access to an outdoor area in forest, woodlands on agriculture land or pastures (see Figure 1 below)
- Pigs have access to an outdoor area on farm premises (adjacent to farm buildings) (see Figure 2 below)

Type of outdoor farm:

1

2

* 31. Did you introduce agriculture machinery and/or equipment potentially in contact with pigs

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within the 6 weeks before confirmation of ASF on the case farm (or the corresponding case farm in case the interview is on a control farm)?

More than one answer is possible

- Yes, purchased new from dealer
 - Yes, second hand or borrowed
 - No
- * 33. Is there a point of disinfection for the wheels at the entrance of the holding?
- Yes
 - No
- * 34. How many visits of professionals on the holding (number of people entering the farm for professional reasons) occurred on average on a daily basis within the 6 weeks before confirmation of ASF on the case farm (or the corresponding case farm in case the interview is on a control farm)?

Private veterinarians:

* Official veterinarians:

* Farm workers:

* Consultants (industry reps...):

* Suppliers of farm utensils/feed:

* Live animal traders:

* Others:

* If OTHERS, please specify which:

* 36. How many visitors (number of people belonging to family, friends, students, entering the farm for personal reasons) entered the holding on average on a daily basis within the 6 weeks before confirmation of ASF on the case farm (or the corresponding case farm in case the interview is on a control farm)?

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visitors

* 37. Was there any unusual event within the 6 weeks before the confirmation of the outbreak on the case farm/on the control farm corresponding to the case farm in case the interview is on a control farm?

More than one answer is possible

- Construction work new building
- Change of staff
- Family/social event
- Break in biosecurity routine
- Other
- No
- I don't know

* If OTHER, please specify which:

* 38. What kind of bedding is used in the sheds?

More than one answer is possible

- Straw
- Wood chips
- Sawdust
- None
- Other

* If OTHER, please specify which:

* 39. Is the holding fenced to avoid contact with wild animals (e.g. wild boar, wolves, foxes, jackals...)?

- Yes
- No

* What type of fence?

- Double fence
- Solid single fence
- Single fence

* 41. Is manure from other holdings spread on neighbouring farmlands situated directly next to your stables (< 500 meters)?

- Yes

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- No
- I don't know

* 42. Were NEW pigs and/or piglets introduced or purchased in the establishment within the 6 weeks before confirmation of ASF on the case farm?

- Yes
- No

* 43. Were pigs sold from the establishment within the 6 weeks before confirmation of ASF on the case farm (or the corresponding case farm in case the interview is on a control farm)?

- Yes
- No

* 44. Were there any possible contacts with case farms within the 6 weeks before confirmation of ASF on the case farm? (e.g. natural mount, artificial insemination, shared material/objects/vehicles, external visitors, etc.)

- Yes
- No
- I am not sure/I do not know

* If yes, please specify the type of contact (e.g. vehicles, people, equipment...):

* 45. Does anyone among the workers of your holding carry out any outdoor activity (in wild boar habitat)?

More than one answer is possible

- Work (forest management, agricultural activities, bee-keeping, ...)
- Leisure (hiking, mountain climbing, mountain biking, bird watching...)
- Hunting
- None of the above I don't know
- Other

* If other, please specify which:

* 46 . Are the workers allowed to bring their own food in the holding?

- Yes
- No

* 47. Does anyone among the workers of your holding have contact to pigs on other farms or in their private life (including other premises owned by you)?

- Yes
- No

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* 48. Can carcasses be collected by the rendering company from the public road, without entering to the premises?

- Yes
- No

* 49. Can the feed be delivered from the public road without entering the premises?

- Yes
- No

* 50. How are pigs loaded, when they leave for selling or slaughter?

- Truck enters farm and pigs can possibly return to shed from the truck
- Truck enters farm and pigs cannot return to shed from the truck
- Truck does not enter farm and pigs cannot return to shed

* 51. Are pig pens accessible to visitors and workers only through the locker room?

- Yes
- No

* 52. Is there a rodent control management plan implemented?

- Yes
- No

* 53. Are there intact insect nets placed in front of the air intakes and the windows in the sheds?

- Yes, on all air intakes and the windows
- Yes, but not on all air intakes and the windows
- No

* If yes, please provide the approximate mesh diameter:

mm

* 54. Do you apply insecticide in or around your pig shed?

- Yes
- No

* If yes, when was an insecticide last applied? (number of days since last application)

days

* 55. What product is used for disinfection of baths/ boot washers/stables at the holding?

Name of commercial product

* 56. Is a quarantine period respected if new pigs arrive or are purchased in your holding?

- Yes

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- No

* If yes, how many days?

days

* 57. Is the procedure all-in/all-out for all pigs on farm implemented?

- Yes
- No

Seasonality

* 58. Do you share any crop harvesting machinery with other pig farmers?

- Yes
- No

* 59. Is there a change in diet of the pigs over summer?

- Yes
- No

* If yes, please specify ...

Open question for case farms

* 60. Is there any other potential risk factor that we did not inquire about, that you consider the possible reason of introduction of the virus on your farm?

Background Documents

[Data Protection Note \[ENG\]](#)

[Data Protection Note \[LT\]](#)

[Data Protection Note \[PL\]](#)

[Data Protection Note \[RO\]](#)

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